

**CHARACTERISTICS OF BENEFITS ADDITIONAL TO POSITION
SALARY AS INCENTIVES IN PUBLIC CIVIL SERVICE****Alisher Nasirdinovich Juraev**

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The new era requires reforms in all areas, so now, from all developed countries to developing countries, public service reform, prevention of staff unemployment, prevention of corruption, and social and economic support of civil servants should be done to improve the attractiveness of public service. A number of changes are being implemented, such as the increase, because the performance of functions and tasks of the state and the high spirit of public services depend on the activity of civil servants.

It is interesting to emphasize that the importance of public service incentives in public service is incomparable in increasing the interest of employees in the service, giving them a motivational spirit, and providing social and economic support to the employee and his family members.

Incentives for civil servants are considered a type of state legal relations, and this relation is regulated by administrative legal norms, but it is worth saying separately that among a number of legal scholars who have studied this field of law, there is a difference of opinion by which legal norms this field of law is regulated. There are different opinions and viewpoints, the reason for this can be justified by considering this field of law as a complex legal network.

Analyzing the scope of legal regulation of civil service issues, S.E. Channov and M.V. Presnyakov stated that currently the legislation on the right to service is very complex and multifaceted¹, By Yu.N. Starilov, legislation on state civil service promotes learning in a separate field of law², By S.E. Channov, he justifies the fact that civil service is not regulated on the basis of labor legislation, that mutual subordination, not equality, plays an important role in this relationship³.

In our opinion, it is appropriate to study this institute in the field of administrative law. There are several reasons for this:

- First, the state civil service and its incentive measures are related to internal management relations of administrative law;

¹ Channov S.E. Presnyakov M.V. Official law: textbook and workshop for bachelor's and specialty students. 2nd ed. M.: Yurayt, 2019. P. 55

² Starilov Yu. N. What is happening to the institution of the Russian public service? // Journal of Russian Law. 2004. No. 9 (93). P. 13

³ Channov S.E. Back to the issue of official law // State and law. 2015. No. 3. P. 10.

- Second, public civil service relations in many developed countries are studied as an institution of administrative law;
- Thirdly, incentives in the state civil service are part of the administrative-legal method of incentives of state management.

In the legal literature, there are two types of bases for motivating civil servants: normative and factual. The normative-legal framework is strengthened in various normative-legal documents and envisages measures to encourage civil servants. These documents can be divided into two groups: laws and statutory documents.

It is interesting to say that currently the legislation regulating public service relations has not been consolidated into a single law, and the object that we want to analyze today, i.e., the norms related to the use of incentive measures in the public service, is not regulated within the framework of a single law in our country. The use of incentive measures in the state civil service is defined in articles 44-45 of the Law "On State Civil Service", Article 44 of the law is called "Incentives for the State Civil Servant", and the following incentive is given to the State Civil Servant incentive measures may be applied:

- additional increments to the position salary;
- prize money;
- awarding extraordinary qualifications;
- declaration of gratitude;
- reward with an expensive gift, memento or badge or label.

It is established that a state civil servant can be presented with state awards for special services in accordance with the procedure established by law.

Setting additional salary increments as an incentive measure is currently the basis for a number of controversial opinions by many legal scholars, the reason for which is the procedure for incentives for labor in Article 299 of the Labor Code. part 4 of this norm stipulates that wages, bonuses, additional payments, bonuses and other payments provided for in the labor remuneration system are not included in the list of types of incentives, therefore, in many state bodies, state citizenship is currently since the register of employees does not exist, the reason is that additional salary increments by applying the labor code are not part of the incentive measure.

However, it is worth noting that the Labor Code does not permanently regulate relations related to civil service, because legal relations of civil service differ from legal relations of labor on the following grounds: according to subjects, according to the object of relations, normative legal according to the

scope of the documents. Subjects of public service can be state bodies and state civil servants, and in labor relations it is possible to see that the employer and the employee enter into a legal relationship. If the Labor Code regulates the relations between the employer and the employee during work, the legislation on public service can also regulate the relations between the public body and the employee outside of the service. According to part 1 of Article 299 of the Labor Code, the types of incentives and the procedure for their application are defined in collective agreements, collective agreements, rules of internal labor procedures and other legal documents on labor and labor contracts, so if the state if additional increases to the salary of the position are mentioned as an incentive in the legal requirements regulating the service, then the application of this measure is considered legal.

If we analyze using a number of legal documents to justify our opinions, the list of civil servants as an appendix to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 03.07.1997 No. 339 "On setting a twenty percent premium to the salaries of civil servants" up to 20% increments can be added to the salaries of employees in this application as an incentive, adopted by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 320 dated 04.17.2019 "The State Tax Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan to Clause 62 of the regulation "on" is devoted to the main types of financial incentives for employees of the state tax service, and according to paragraph 4, the salaries of employees are increased for the complexity and importance of the work area and for achieving high results in work. If the procedure is given, special incentive bonuses are determined for the salaries of the employees of the state tax service, based on the performance of their functional duties, the level of knowledge, and the professional skills of working with taxpayers. in addition, a number of other similar laws and by-laws mention the possibility of setting additional increases to the salary of the position as an incentive.

From the above-mentioned points, we can draw a conclusion that in the regulation of relations related to the public service, it is appropriate to proceed from the law "On State Civil Service" and the legislative requirements regulating special service, and the aspects not regulated by the law are regulated by the labor code. must be milked.

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